

UN SECURITY COUNCIL SANCTIONS AGAINST TERRORISM AND HUMAN RIGHTS

Hakimov Sherzod

Master's student of the Department of Labor Law,
Tashkent State University of Law
+998915631971
sherzodhakimov71@icloud.com
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Abstract. This article analyzes UN Security Council anti-terrorism sanctions and human rights. It will also discuss the improvement of preventive mechanisms aimed at preventing the factors that cause extremism and terrorism, improving the social and spiritual environment, preventing the influence of foreign ideas, and eliminating their problems through systematic work with those affected by such influence.

Key words: UN Security Council, terrorism, human rights, development, strategy, extremism, criminal activity, potential of states, aggression, international peace, security.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada BMT xavfsizlik kengashining terrorizmga qarshi sanksiyalari va inson huquqlari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, ekstremizm va terrorizmni keltirib chiqaruvchi omillarning oldini olishga qaratilgan preventiv mexanizmlarni takomillashtirish, ijtimoiy-ma'naviy muhitni yaxshilash, yot g'oyalar ta'sirining oldini olish va bunday ta'sirga tushib qolganlar bilan tizimli ishlash orqali ularning muammolarini bartaraf etish muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: BMT xavfsizlik kengashi, terrorizm, inson huquqlari, taraqqiyot, strategiya, ekstremizm, jinoiy faoliyat, davlatlar salohiyati, agressiya, xalqaro tinchlik, xavfsizlik.

Абстракт. В данной статье анализируются антитеррористические санкции Совета Безопасности ООН и права человека. Также будет обсуждено совершенствование превентивных механизмов, направленных на предотвращение факторов, вызывающих экстремизм и терроризм, улучшение социальной и духовной среды, предотвращение влияния иностранных идей, устранение их проблем посредством систематической работы с теми, кто пострадал от такого влияния.

Ключевые слова: Совет Безопасности ООН, терроризм, права человека, развитие, стратегия, экстремизм, преступная деятельность, потенциал государств, агрессия, международный мир, безопасность.

Terrorism - in order to achieve political, religious, ideological and other goals, endangers the life and health of a person, causes the risk of destruction (damage) of property and other material objects and threatens the state, international organization, physical or to compel a legal entity to commit or refrain from committing any actions, to complicate international relations, to violate the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the state, to undermine its security, to provoke armed conflicts, to intimidate the population, to affect the socio-political situation violence, threat of violence or other criminal acts aimed at destabilization, for which responsibility is provided in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The United Nations Security Council is the main permanent political body of the UN; According to Article 24 of the UN Charter, the main responsibility for maintaining international peace and security rests with the UN Security Council.

The scope of activities of the UN Security Council is clearly defined in the UN Charter and broad powers are given in the field of peaceful settlement of disputes between states. It has the authority to investigate any dispute or situation likely to cause international conflicts or conflicts, to determine any threat to the peace and any violation of it or cases of aggression, and to determine appropriate measures and make recommendations regarding the maintenance or restoration of international peace and security.

There are 15 UN member states: 5 permanent and 10 temporary members. According to Article 23 of the UN Charter, the United States, Great Britain, France, China, the United Kingdom of Northern Ireland and Russia are permanent members of the UN Security Council. Temporary members are elected by the General Assembly for a 2-year term, and 5 temporary members must be re-elected at each session.

Provisional members are distributed according to their seats: 5 members from Asian and African countries, 1 member from Eastern European countries, 2 members from Latin American countries, Western Europe and other countries (Canada, Australia, New Zealand). - 2 members. Each member state of the UN Security Council has one representative. The UN Security Council works continuously, the breaks between its meetings must not exceed 2 weeks. At these meetings, the representative of the countries in alphabetical order by their official name in English presides over a period of one month.

UN Security Council meetings will be open; except for cases where the meeting is declared closed due to valid reasons.

One of the four main parts of the UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy, adopted on September 8, 2006, is devoted to the topic of human rights. It should be noted that this section is entitled "Measures to ensure universal respect for human rights and the rule of law as the main pillar of the fight against terrorism." As recognized in the Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy, effective measures to combat terrorism and protect human rights do not negate the other. On the contrary, they complement each other and are extremely necessary to support and protect the rights of victims of terrorism.

It should also be noted that it is not for nothing that the sixth priority direction in the "**Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026**" is called "Approaching universal problems based on national interests".

- improvement of preventive mechanisms aimed at preventing the factors that cause extremism and terrorism, improving the social and spiritual environment, preventing the influence of foreign ideas and eliminating their problems through systematic work with those affected by such influences;
- formation of strong and stable immunity against the ideology of terrorism and extremism among the population, especially the young generation;
- improvement of the international legal basis of combating extremism and terrorism and expansion of the contractual legal basis of cooperation with foreign countries, regional and international organizations in the field of combating extremism and terrorism;
- strengthening the personnel capacity and resources of diplomatic missions and consular institutions, the Agency for Foreign Labor Migration, as well as other agencies dealing with citizens who are going abroad for a long time and living abroad;
- exchange of information and experience with foreign countries and international organizations in the field of combating extremism, terrorism and their financing;
- active participation in international and regional organizations whose activities are aimed at combating extremism and terrorism;
- Coordination of joint efforts to implement the UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy in Central Asia within the framework of the joint action plan;
- Expanding the role of Uzbekistan in the implementation of international initiatives that help to develop information exchange and cooperation

within the framework of joint efforts to fight extremism and terrorism in Central Asia;

- consistent work has been initiated within the framework of important issues such as the acceleration of initiatives to attract the attention of the world community and regional organizations to the maintenance of peace and harmony in Afghanistan and the involvement of this country in regional cooperation processes, including the fight against extremism and terrorism.

The fact that a lot of attention is being paid to human rights issues is in harmony with the principle of "For human dignity" put forward by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev on the way to building New Uzbekistan.

This is clearly confirmed by the fact that the topic "Global respect for human rights and ensuring the rule of law - the main support of the fight against terrorism" will be discussed in a separate session within the framework of the conference.

Our country has supported the UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy, ratified 14 international conventions and protocols on combating terrorism and religious extremism.

In addition, in this regard, in our country there are laws "On Combating Extremism", "On Combating Terrorism", "On Combating Legalization of Proceeds from Criminal Activities, Financing Terrorism and Financing the Distribution of Weapons of Mass Destruction" Laws and other regulatory legal documents have been adopted.

The UN and Uzbekistan: cooperation in the fight against terrorism and human rights. On December 16, 2021, at the 76th session of the UN General Assembly, Resolution No. 76/169 entitled "Terrorism and Human Rights" was adopted. In the resolution, terrorism and all attacks, methods and practices of violent extremism that create conditions for terrorism, in what form and form they occur, where and by whom they are carried out, and on the basis of what motivation or financial, material or political support they are carried out. regardless, it is emphasized that it will be unconditionally condemned as a behavior that is completely incompatible with international law.

The Resolution of the UN General Assembly also emphasizes that terrorism and violent extremism that create conditions for terrorism are an obstacle to the full realization of human rights, freedoms and legitimate interests. Due to these negative factors, on the one hand, there are obstacles to the realization of the political, personal, economic, social and cultural rights of a person, and on the

other hand, the territorial integrity and security of states, the stability of governments, the priority of law and democracy are more worrying. , the existence of prosperous societies, international peace and security in the world will be under great threat.

In addition, in resolution 76/169, the governments of all countries are required to provide full support to the UN Human Rights Council Special Rapporteur on the promotion and protection of human rights in the fight against terrorism in fulfilling the tasks and obligations assigned to him, asked to show.

At this point, it is appropriate to briefly mention the fact that during the visit of the UN Special Rapporteur Fionnuala Ni Aolain to our country from November 28 to December 7, 2021, Uzbekistan worked closely with her.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev received UN Special Rapporteur F.Ni Aolain. During the dialogue, it was agreed to hold a number of joint international events aimed at strengthening the partnership of Uzbekistan with UN bodies and human rights institutions.

The UN Special Rapporteur, in his dialogue with the President of Uzbekistan, as well as at the press conference and briefings with the participation of the general public, highly appreciated the efforts of Uzbekistan to return citizens to the country, rehabilitation and reintegration within the framework of Operation "Mehr".

F.Ni Aolain visited the rehabilitation center for persons returning from Syria, Iraq and Afghanistan. In this place in the Bostanliq district of the Tashkent region, he got acquainted with the conditions created for the rehabilitation of women and children who were taken out of "hot spots" in time.

"The Uzbek model, based on family unity and community support, is a best practice example of repatriation, child welfare and effective reintegration of women returning from hotbed areas at the center of political, legal and social action," he said. UN Special Rapporteur.

It is known that representatives of Uzbekistan participated in the online event organized on the topic of "Rehabilitation and reintegration of women and children brought from Syria and Iraq" within the framework of the 47th session of the UN Human Rights Council on July 5, 2021.

In this seminar, it was noted with concern that nearly 70,000 people - mostly women and children, citizens of 57 countries - are being kept in dire conditions in the camps "Al-Hol" and "Raj" located in the north-eastern part of Syria.

It is worth noting that since 2019, Uzbekistan has conducted five "Mehr" operations to return women and children from Syria, Iraq and Afghanistan. A total of 531 people were brought to the country from conflict areas.

The international community welcomed Uzbekistan's efforts to repatriate and reintegrate its citizens from conflict zones, including Iraq and Syria. It was recognized that there are few countries that have shown such activity as Uzbekistan in such efforts.

According to international experts, these efforts are extremely important because they are based on the recognition of children as victims and the need to protect their individual interests through gender-sensitive community-level reintegration programs for children and women.

More importantly, these efforts, through strong technical assistance and human capacity building, serve to promote human rights, promote democracy and strengthen the rule of law.

The reintegration of children, women and families who have returned to their homeland into society, on the one hand, will end their social isolation, and on the other hand, will strengthen peace and stability in society by reducing poverty.

The UN Special Rapporteur, F.Ni Aolain, noted the new approaches in the fight against terrorism and extremism. Consequently, Uzbekistan actively participates in the fight against terrorism in the international arena. International anti-terrorist coalitions consistently support their activities. In particular, our country has been participating in the activities of the UN Anti-Terrorism Committee and the CIS Anti-Terrorism Center.

In conclusion, the Tashkent international conference will present the unique experience of the cooperation of the Central Asian countries on the implementation of the UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy.

It is also expected that the conference will discuss the prospects of expanding the role of the UN in unifying international and regional efforts in the fight against terrorism, strengthening the capacity of states, ensuring human rights and the rule of law in these complex processes.

Currently, within the framework of the Development Strategy, including:

- improvement of preventive mechanisms aimed at preventing the factors that cause extremism and terrorism, improving the social and spiritual environment, preventing the influence of foreign ideas and eliminating their problems through systematic work with those affected by such influences;

- formation of strong and stable immunity against the ideology of terrorism and extremism among the population, especially the young generation;
- improvement of the international legal basis of combating extremism and terrorism and expansion of the contractual legal basis of cooperation with foreign countries, regional and international organizations in the field of combating extremism and terrorism;
- strengthening the personnel capacity and resources of diplomatic missions and consular institutions, the Agency for Foreign Labor Migration, as well as other agencies dealing with citizens who are going abroad and living abroad for a long time;
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- active participation in international and regional organizations whose activities are aimed at combating extremism and terrorism;
- coordination of joint efforts to implement the UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy in Central Asia within the framework of the joint action plan;
- Expanding the role of Uzbekistan in the implementation of international initiatives that help to develop information exchange and cooperation within the framework of joint efforts to fight against extremism and terrorism in Central Asia;
- consistent work has been initiated within the framework of important issues such as accelerating initiatives to attract the attention of the world community and regional organizations to ensuring peace and harmony in Afghanistan and involving this country in regional cooperation processes, including the fight against extremism and terrorism.

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